

Study of Clinicodemographic Profile in Children with Acute CNS Infection and Its Correlation with NeuroimagingSaunil N Shah¹, Katha Vyas², Tirth Vyas³, Sanya Shah⁴¹Resident Doctor, Department of Anaesthesiology, MG Hospital, RVRS Medical College, Bhilwara, Rajasthan, India²Resident Doctor, Department of Paediatrics, NHL Medical College, Ahmedabad, Gujarat, India³Intern Doctor, B J Medical College, Ahmedabad, Gujarat, India⁴Second Year MBBS Student, Banas Medical College & Research Institute, Palanpur, Gujarat, India

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: Infection of the central nervous system (CNS) is the most common cause of fever that is associated with signs and symptoms of CNS disease in children. Viral infections of the CNS are much more common than bacterial infections, which, in turn, are more common than fungal and parasitic infections. Radiology and pathology are inseparable at the time of understanding the phenomenon causing nervous system infections. There are a wide range of neuroimaging findings in central nervous system (CNS) infections, often with considerable overlap, which makes determination of a specific diagnosis difficult. The present study aims to study the utility of neuroimaging in diagnosis of acute CNS infection and the neuroimaging patterns found in different CNS infection

Aim: 1. To study the utility of neuroimaging in CNS infection in paediatric age group. 2. To study the pattern of neuroimaging in children in CNS infection. 3. To study the socio demographic and clinical profile of CNS infection in children

Method: This is prospective observational study in children (1month – 14 years old) who are presented with CNS infection.

Result: Total 116 cases of less than 14 years old children were suspected to have CNS infection in study period at a tertiary care center. It was observed that acute CNS infection was more prevalent in 1 month -1 year age group with (27.58%), followed by 5 - 8 year (24.13%), 1- 8 year (20.68%) and 3-5 year (5.17%). In this study neuroimaging was done in all suspected cases (116) of CNS infection in which 55.91(48.2%) patients had normal neuroimaging study and 60(51.7%) had abnormal neuroimaging study. Among the cases with abnormal neuroimaging 6 (10%) showed pyogenic meningitis, tubercular meningitis was present in 14 (23.23%) patients, tuberculoma in 8 (13.13%), TBM + tuberculoma in 6 (10%), viral meningitis in 8 (13.3%), HSE in 2 (3.3%), COVID encephalitis in 2(3.3%), ADEM in 8 (13.3%) while 4 patients (6.66%) were found to have brain abscess. Correlation between final diagnosis and neuroimaging was 100% in ADEM, Brain abscess, tuberculoma, TB spine, HSV followed by TBM 77.77% and followed by pyogenic meningitis (27.27%) and viral encephalitis (26.66%). Clinically diagnosed acute CNS infection was confirmed in 51.72% (60 case) and was wrong in 48.27% (56 case).

Conclusion: CNS infections were more common in less than 5 years age. Around half of the patients had abnormal neuroimaging finding. Neuroimaging studies are helpful to monitor the complications such as subdural effusion, hydrocephalus, infarction etc. It was found that neuro-imaging was accurate in early diagnosis and categorization of CNS infections with high sensitivity in CNS tuberculosis.

Keywords: CNS infection, neuroimaging, paediatrics.

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Introduction

Infection of the central nervous system (CNS) is the most common cause of fever associated with signs and symptoms of CNS disease in children. Viral infections of the CNS are much more common than

bacterial infections, which, in turn, are more common than fungal and parasitic infections.

Radiology and pathology are inseparable at the time of understanding the phenomenon causing nervous

system infections. There are a wide range of neuroimaging findings in central nervous system (CNS) infections, often with considerable overlap, which makes determination of a specific diagnosis difficult. Correlation with laboratory tests, particularly cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) analysis, is considered to be essential in establishing a definitive diagnosis. [1]

Most patients with CNS infection have similar clinical manifestations. Common symptoms include headache, nausea, vomiting, anorexia, restlessness, altered state of consciousness, and irritability; most of these symptoms are nonspecific [2]. Common signs of CNS infection, in addition to fever, include photophobia, neck pain and rigidity, obtundation, stupor, coma, seizures, and focal neurologic deficits. [2].

Infection of the CNS may be diffuse or focal. Meningitis and encephalitis are examples of diffuse infection. Meningitis implies primary involvement of the meninges, whereas encephalitis indicates brain parenchymal involvement.

Because these anatomic boundaries are often not distinct, many patients have evidence of both meningeal and parenchymal involvement and should be considered to have meningoenkephalitis. Brain abscess is the best example of a focal infection of the CNS [3]. The diagnosis of diffuse CNS infections depends on examination of cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) obtained by lumbar puncture (LP). Though CSF remains the gold standard for diagnosis of acute CNS infection, role of neuroimaging cannot be denied. Few Indian studies are available which delineate the efficacy and accuracy of neuroimaging

in management of patient with acute CNS infection. The present study aims to study the utility of neuroimaging in diagnosis of acute CNS infection and the neuroimaging patterns found in different CNS infection.

Material & Method

1) Study Design: This is prospective observational study in children (1month – 14 years old) who presented with CNS infection.

2) Study Population: Children between 1 month-14 years of age.

3) Study place: Ward and PICU of tertiary care teaching hospital.

4) Selection Criteria: following inclusion and exclusion criteria was used to select the study subjects

A) Inclusion Criteria: All children between age of 1 month to 14 years admitted in ward and PICU of tertiary care center were diagnosed as having CNS infection based on clinical and neuroimaging findings. Neuroimaging was done in all suspected cases of CNS infection.

B) Exclusion Criteria: Patient expired within 24 hour of admission. Those patients who are clinically suspected for acute CNS infection but not affordable for Neuro-imaging.

Result

Total 116 cases of less than 14 years old children were suspected to have CNS infection in study period at a tertiary care center.

Table 1: Age and sex Group Distribution

Age group	No. of cases	%
1 month -1 year	32	27.58
1 - < 3 year	26	22.41
3-<5 year	6	5.17
5-<8 year	28	24.13
>8 year	24	20.68
Total	116	100
Sex group		
Male	60	51.72
Female	56	48.27
Total	116	100

Table 2: Clinical Presentation

Symptoms	Yes	%
Fever	90	77.58
Altered sensorium	36	31.03
Seizure	100	86.20
Vomiting	34	29.31
Headache	18	15.51
Cough- Cold	4	13.79
Refusal to feed/Decrease oral intake	22	18.19
Status epilepticus	60	60
Meningeal signs	68	58.62

In this study, among the 116 cases, fever was present in 90 (77.58%), Altered sensorium in 36 (31.03%), seizures in 100 (86.20%), vomiting was present in 34(29.31%), headache in 18(15.51%) and cough-cold in 16 (13.79%) cases. out of 100 cases with seizures 60% had status epilepticus. 68 (58.62 %

cases had signs of meningeal irritation while in 48 (41.37%) cases signs were absent.

Around half of the patient had meningeal signs because both meningitis and encephalitis are included as part of spectrum of acute CNS infection.

Table 3: Spectrum of Acute CNS Infection

Diagnosis	Case	%
Pyogenic meningitis	22	18.96
Enteric encephalitis	6	5.17
CNS TB	32	27.5
a. TBM	18	
b. Tuberculoma	8	
c. TBM+tuberculoma	6	
TB Spine	2	1.72
Viral meningoencephalitis	28	24.13
Herpes simplex encephalitis	2	1.72
Dengue encephalitis	10	8.62
COVID encephalitis	2	1.72
ADEM	8	6.89
Brain abscess	4	3.44
Total	116	100

In this study on distributing patients based on clinical and pathological findings, viral infection 28 (24.13%) was most common, followed by acute bacterial/ pyogenic infection 22 (18.96%), tubercular infection 32 (27.5%), dengue encephalitis in 10 (8.62%), enteric encephalitis 6 (5.13%), TB spine and HSE, COVID encephalitis in 2(1.72%).

Figure 1: Number of patient with Abnormal Neuroimaging

Among the 60 cases with abnormal neuroimaging 6 (10%) showed pyogenic meningitis. In CNS TB: tubercular meningitis present in 14 (23.23%) patient, tuberculoma in 8 (13.13%), TBM +

tuberculoma in 6 (10%).Viral meningitis in 8 (13.3%), HSE in 2 (3.3%), COVID encephalitis in 2 (3.3%), ADEM in 8 (13.3%) while 4 patients (6.66%) were found to have brain abscess.

Table 4: Comparisons of Final Diagnosis and Neuroimaging

CNS Infection	Final Diagnosis	Abnormal neuroimaging finding	Correlation
Pyogenic meningitis	22	6	27.27
Enteric encephalitis	6	0	0
CNS TB	32	28	87.5
A. TBM	18	14	77.77
B. Tuberculoma	8	8	100
C. TBM+tuberculoma	6	6	100
TB SPINE	2	2	100
Viral meningitis	0	0	0
Herpes simplex encephalitis	30	8	26.66
Dengue encephalitis	2	2	100
COVID encephalitis	10	0	0
ADEM	2	2	100
Brain abscess	8	8	100
Total	4	4	100

Figure 2: Comparisons of final diagnosis and neuroimaging

Clinically diagnosed was confirmed in 51.72% (60 case) and was wrong in 48.27% (56 case). There was significant statistical correlation between abnormal neuroimaging findings and etiology of CNS infections. Correlation is significantly more in case

of Tuberculous meningitis as compared to pyogenic meningitis ($p < 0.05$). Was 100% in ADEM, Brain abscess, tuberculoma, TB spine, HSV followed by TBM 77.77% and followed by pyogenic meningitis (27.27%) and viral encephalitis (26.66%).

Table 5: Comparison for Sensitivity of neuroimaging in CNS infection

Sensitivity for	Present Study	Kumar R(2015)	Granerod Et Al	Mei-Ling Sharon TAI Et Al	Dongfeng Zhang(2017)(MRI+CSF)	Olivier a Cret AI(MRI +CSF)
Tb	88.2	14.2	-	-	24.75	81.3
Pyogenic Meningitis	30	88.5	-	89	62.46	-
Viral Encephalitis	28.5	26.6	81	-	68.71	68.71

Sensitivity was highest in TBM and lower in case of pyogenic meningitis and viral encephalitis, which was comparable to other study.

This was prospective observational study in children (1month - 14 year old) who presented with CNS infection .This study included 116 children in the age group of 1 month– 14 years with a clinical picture suggestive of CNS infection.

Discussion

Shah *et al.*

Acute CNS infection found to be more prevalent in 1 month -1 year group (27.58 %), followed by 5 - 8 year (24.13%), 1-<3 year (22.41%), > 8 year (20.68%), and 3-5 year (5.17%). The results are comparable with study done at. Ananthapuri Hospital and Research Institute, Thiruvananthapuram, India between 2008 and 2020 where 16 patient in the infant (1 month -1year old) group (25.80%) and 27 patient (43.54%) in the age group 1-5 year. [4]

Among the 116 cases, fever was present in 90 (77.58%), Altered sensorium in 36 (31.03%), seizures in 100 (86.20%), vomiting was present in 34(29.31%). Thus, fever, altered sensorium and seizures, which is considered to be the triad of symptoms in acute CNS infections, was present in most of the cases. This study was compared with the “Clinico-etiological correlation with the neuroimaging study” in Dhiraj Hospital, Vadodara. Fever was the most common presenting symptom and was present in all patients followed by convulsion (73.77%), altered sensorium (36.07%), vomiting (31.15%), irritability 17 (27.87%) and headache (18%) respectively. [5]

Out of 100 cases with seizure, 60% had status epilepticus. 68 (58.62%) cases had signs of meningeal irritation. The results are comparable with study done at. Ananthapuri Hospital and Research Institute, Thiruvananthapuram, India between 2008 and 2020 were out of 24 pt, 14 patients (58.33%) presented with status epilepticus, and it is the most common symptom. [4]

Distributing patients based on clinical and pathological findings, viral infection (24.13%) was most common followed by acute bacterial/pyogenic infection (18.96%), tubercular infection 16 (27.5%), dengue encephalitis in (8.62%), TB spine and HSE in (1.72%). This study compared with the imaging of CNS Infections with clinic-pathological correlation, done at Western Uttar Pradesh where tubercular infection (TBM) was most common (41.2%) followed by acute bacterial/ pyogenic infection (36.2%) and viral infection (22.5%) [6] Thus, commonest CNS infection encountered in the present study was viral meningitis followed by pyogenic meningitis which was closely followed by pyogenic meningitis.

Out of 116 patient 56 (48.2%) patients had normal neuroimaging study and 60(51.7%) had abnormal neuroimaging study. Among the cases with abnormal neuroimaging 6 (10%) showed pyogenic meningitis, tubercular meningitis was present in 14 (23.23%) patients, tuberculoma in 8 (13.13%), TBM + tuberculoma in 6(10%), viral meningitis in 8 (13.3%), HSE in 2 (3.3%), COVID encephalitis in 2(3.3%), ADEM in 8 (13.3%) while 4 patients (6.66%) were found to have brain abscess. Thus, out of the patients with abnormal neuroimaging in the

present study, maximum number of patients was of CNS tuberculosis, followed by viral meningitis and ADEM. Pyogenic meningitis was found in around 1/10th of the patients.

Clinico-neuroimaging correlation was seen in ADEM, Brain abscess (100%), and followed by CNS TB (77.77%), pyogenic meningitis (27.27%), viral meningoencephalitis (26.66%). Thus neuroimaging remain modality of choice for diagnosis of ADEM, brain abscess, TB spine, tuberculoma, HSE. This fact is confirmed in the study. Also correlation was significantly more in TBM as compared to pyogenic meningitis.

Conclusions

CNS infections were more common in less than 5 years age. Fever, altered sensorium and seizures, which is considered to be the triad of symptoms in acute CNS infections, was present in most of the cases. Around half of the patients had abnormal neuroimaging finding. It was found that neuro-imaging was accurate in early diagnosis and categorization of CNS infections with high sensitivity in CNS tuberculosis. In patients presenting with CNS infection, familiarity of various imaging patterns in CNS infections is of key importance to paediatricians and radiologists in timely diagnosis thereby reduce irrational over use of antibiotic and antiviral medication, morbidity and mortality of the potential threatening disease.

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